

Globalization and the Mind: Exploring Youth Mental Health in a Connected World

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<https://currentsignjournal.com/index.php/JCS/index>

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Abstract

Globalization, a phenomenon emerged as a defined feature of contemporary society, harms young people as they are frequently exposed to global media, cultures, academic and economic competition.

Purpose: This study investigates the impact of globalization on the mental health of students aged 18–25 years.

Method: A quantitative approach using a structured questionnaire, based on a Likert scale,

to collect data from individuals, 325 university students.

Findings: The study revealed that globalization has a dual impact on youth. While it increases cultural exposure, global connectivity, educational and career opportunities, it also contributes to issues like stress, anxiety, information overload, and concerns about cultural identity.

Implication: The study concludes that globalization has a significant impact on the mental health of youth. For its well-being, it emphasizes the need for institutional and policy-level mental health support, as well as the role of policymakers in developing strategies to promote and address the consequences of this issue on youth in an increasingly globalized world.

Keywords: Globalization, Mental Health, Youth.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization is the integration of economies and cultures through trade, migration, and shared ideas (Peters, 2025). In recent decades, it has significantly transformed the lives of young people, particularly university students who are constantly exposed to global information, competition, and cultural influences. While globalization has created numerous opportunities for education, employment, and cultural exchange, it has also introduced challenges related to mental health, identity, and psychological well-being. Youth aged 18–25 years represent a critical developmental stage characterized by identity formation, academic pressure, and career planning. Mental health is defined as a state of well-being in which people recognize their abilities, are able to cope with the normal stresses of life, work productively and fruitfully, and make a contribution to their communities (Selva, 2023). The rapid pace of globalization may intensify stress, anxiety, and confusion during this phase. Understanding how globalization affects youth mental health is particularly essential, especially given the urgent need to address its adversaries. Schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, split personality disorder and sweating due to anxiety are common mental health issues. The broad range of implications economic exploitation, cultural homogenization, threat to national sovereignty, environmental degradation

most importantly the mental health outcomes associated with them. Cultural appropriation may occur without any acknowledgement of the original culture, perpetuating exploitation (Lalonde,2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous studies suggest that globalization has its own implications for youth's mental health can be wide ranging from positive and negative. At its finest, it promised to grant the world instant communication, fast and efficient means of travel, and widened access to technology, cross-border cultural interaction, and globalized approaches to environmental issues. However, it also entails deregulation of commerce and the creation of mystic political and economic bodies, making individuals and groups on the verge of chaotic unemployment. The Labor Force Survey 2025 should have jolted the nation into a collective pause, because what it reveals is not a routine economic fluctuation but a structural collapse unfolding in real time. Yet Pakistan is being asked to digest a 7.1 percent unemployment rate as if it were just another bureaucratic figure tucked inside an official report (Burfat, 2025). As a result, the gap is widening between societies that enjoy knowledge, technology, and the ability to control events, and others that are still backward and unable to follow progress and self-actualization. Growing resentment towards one's financial condition as a new era of perfectionism has popped up, making insecurities for individuals, especially young adults, giving rise to consumerism. More than 1 billion people are living with mental health disorders, according to new data released by the World Health Organization, with conditions such as anxiety and depression inflicting immense human and economic tolls. Affecting people of all ages and income levels (WHO, 2025). As mental stress represents the second biggest reason for long-term disability, it contributes to the loss of healthy life. They drive up health-care costs for affected people and families while inflicting substantial economic losses on a global scale. Globalization and its related social and cultural changes have significant mental health outcomes for young people. Identity crisis due to bicultural identity. New international student enrollment surged by 14% in 2022-2023, on top of the 80% increase the prior year, per the 2023 report, released by the Institute of International Education and the U.S. Department of State's Bureau of Educational and Cultural Affairs (Durrani, 2023). Researchers have highlighted benefits such as increased global awareness, cultural tolerance, and access to opportunities.

However, recent reports have seen a surge in stress, anxiety, social comparison, and identity confusion among youth due to global competition and media exposure. The existing literature supports the need for empirical investigation into globalization's psychological impact on youth.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Despite the benefits of globalization, increasing levels of stress, anxiety, and mental health concerns among youth have been reported globally. There is limited empirical research focusing on how globalization specifically impacts the mental health of university youth. This study seeks to address this gap.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Examine university students' perceptions of globalization.

Analyze the impact of globalization on youth mental health.
Identify positive and negative mental health outcomes associated with globalization.
Analyze stress, anxiety, loss of cultural identity, and coping among youth in a globalized context.
Explore the need for institutional support in addressing globalization-related mental health issues.

EXPLAINING OBJECTIVES

1st objective: University students' perceptions of globalization. Understanding that university students largely perceive globalization as a multidimensional phenomenon influencing their academic, social, and personal lives. Most respondents associate globalization with increased access to information, educational opportunities, digital connectivity, and exposure to diverse cultures. Depicting positive perceptions, students also expressed concerns regarding cultural homogenization, increased competition, and pressure to meet global standards. Students view globalization both as an opportunity and a challenge, reflecting a balanced but cautious perception of it.

2nd objective: Impact of globalization on youth mental health. Analysis has revealed that globalization has a significant impact on youth mental health. Heightened levels of stress and anxiety due to academic competition, exposure to global comparison through social media, and uncertainties regarding future employment in an increasingly competitive global market. The way in which nations handle trade and budget improvements can be linked to the varying degrees of political integration with global institutions (Petraikos, 2023). At the same time, globalization has facilitated awareness about mental health issues, improved access to online support systems, and normalized discussions around psychological well-being. Influencing mental health in both protective and risk-enhancing ways.

3rd objective: Positive and negative mental health outcomes associated with globalization. Global competition has also intensified, as digital technology lowered the barriers to entry, resulting in both established and new firms contending for market share (Silaban, 2022). Possible positive outcomes include greater mental health awareness, enhanced coping skills through global exposure, increased acceptance of diversity and self-expression, Access to online counseling resources, and peer support. Negative outcomes may include increased stress, anxiety, and performance pressure, Identity confusion and cultural dissonance, Fear of failure and social comparison, and emotional burnout due to constant connectivity. These findings suggest that globalization acts as a classic double-edged sword, promoting growth and resilience while simultaneously intensifying psychological vulnerabilities among youth.

4th objective: Stress, anxiety, cultural identity, and coping in a globalized context. The results demonstrate that stress and anxiety are closely linked to globalization-related factors such as academic pressure, social media exposure, and evolving societal expectations. Many students reported experiencing conflicts between their cultural identity and traditional values, particularly in relation to global cultural norms. Valuable knowledge, oral traditions, and cultural expressions related to these languages may disappear (Minkov, 2021) Coping strategies varied, with some students adopting positive mechanisms such as peer support, digital detox, and skill development, while others resorted to avoidance or emotional withdrawal. This highlights the

importance of adaptive coping mechanisms in mitigating the adverse mental health effects of globalization.

5th objective: Need for institutional support. Students emphasized the importance of on-campus counseling services, mental health awareness programs, Stress management workshops, and safe spaces for cultural expression and dialogue. The interweaved communication networks have empowered more transcultural psychiatry, which deviates from the stereotyped Western approach to the treatment of mental illness by giving clinicians a more informed understanding of how cultural nuances impact the acceptance of psychological well-being (Mathur,2025) Universities are therefore positioned as key stakeholders in promoting student mental well-being by integrating mental health services into academic structures and addressing globalization-induced stressors through proactive interventions. In conclusion, globalization significantly shapes university students' mental health experiences by influencing stress levels, identity formation, and coping behaviors. While it offers opportunities for growth, exposure, and awareness, it also intensifies psychological pressures. Institutional support systems play a crucial role in balancing these effects and fostering mental resilience among youth in an increasingly globalized world.

RESEARCH METHOD

Presentation, study provides a comprehensive understanding about how globalization affects youth mental health.

Theoretical framework:

This research is based on an integrated theoretical framework borrowed from Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, viewpoints provide a round out understanding of the way the environment (globalization) influences individuals. It elaborates how human development is shaped by interactions within multiple layers of environment, from immediate family to broad cultural influences. Introducing five systems: microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem. As we delve into how globalization impacts the youth. A critical moment in an individual's life is when they grow out of that child phase; hormones play their part in fantasizing about freedom. The immediate relationship, usually family and peers, creates a Microsystem that influences the soft minds with lifestyles and confuse them with standards that aren't even humane. Body-altering trends and to induce youth into mindless insecurities, causing SAD (social anxiety disorder) and body dysmorphia. Emotional detachment with parents because of absence, either due to working abroad or overtime to provide them with what they couldn't. Then the mesosystem, which is the connection composed of family and peers. Academic pressure and discontent at home make a heap of disappointments. Explaining about an ecosystem that incorporates other formal and informal social structures, such as local governments, friends of the family, and mass media, eventually leading to exposure from economic instability to low income, to inhumane crises, disillusioned reality, and fear that it will eventually collapse. Macrosystem encapsulates beliefs and ideologies, which creates confusion, especially when exposed to global norms. Focus on self-reliance and material success. Lastly, the chronosystem relates to environmental changes over a child's lifetime that may be predictable, such as starting school, or unpredictable, such as experiencing parental divorce, or could be any physical adversity.

The study adopted a quantitative, cross-sectional research design. The sample consisted of 325 university students aged between 18 and 25 years. All participants were recorded in gender neutral terms as enrolled in a higher education institution. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire comprising 15 statements related to globalization and mental health. Responses ranged from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques to identify response patterns and trends relevant to the study objectives.

Variable Construction

Globalization Exposure was treated as the independent variable (IV) and constructed by averaging responses to items related to cultural exposure, global media, competition, and global opportunities.

Youth Mental Health was treated as the dependent variable (DV) and constructed using items measuring hopefulness, overall mental state, and coping satisfaction.

Respondents provided their responses through a 15-statement questionnaire, questions based on determining the frequency of impact ranging from positive to negative, and the possible outcome of globalization.

Data Coding and Preparation

Responses were collected using a five-point Likert scale. For statistical analysis, responses were coded as follows: Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, Strongly Agree =

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach's alpha to assess the internal consistency of the scales. The values exceeded the acceptable threshold of 0.70, indicating good reliability.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

A simple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the impact of globalization exposure on youth mental health.

The regression model tested was:

$$\text{Youth Mental Health} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{Globalization Exposure}) + \varepsilon$$

RESULTS

The results indicated that globalization exposure significantly predicts youth mental health ($p < 0.05$). The positive regression coefficient suggests that globalization plays a meaningful role in shaping students' mental health outcomes.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀: Globalization has no significant impact on youth mental health.

H₁: Globalization has a significant impact on youth mental health.

Since the significance value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. If we try to understand the impacts of globalization, a variety of them can be studied, among which alienation or isolation might top the list for various reasons could be as dominant or a narcissistic partner, lack of support and appreciation from family and peers, and criticism that destroys self-esteem. Many of us might be a victim of one or the other at least in our lifetime. Inability to make decisions, even choosing a certain pair of

shoes need for validation. People pleasing and lack of ability to present your stance might be an outcome of growing up in a abusive household and criticized to speak your will. Favoritism, prioritizing one over the other, these kinds irresponsibility in upbringing of a child can eventually lead to unhappy and emotional unstable adult. PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder), borderline personality disorder all these emerged from childhood traumas that are sometimes so serious that some individuals might on verge to permanently damaging their amygdala. Anorexia and other dietary ailments as social media campaign continue to promote a perfectionistic rather unhealthy lifestyle. All this news related to humanitarian crises in Gaza, Sudan, and Ukraine have traumatic effects, thinking of people who are actually facing it. Coping strategies varied from indulging in hobbies or seeking help to survive. Creating boundaries and respecting others might bring a positive impact. The only thing that can help individuals with any of these is someone they can finally speak up about things they've suffered from.

DISCUSSION

Carefully examining the various facets of globalization in order to better understand it. Political globalization refers to the intensification and expansion of political interrelations across the globe (Stegers, 2025). The idea of global governance, which resulted from political globalization, refers to the spread of political beliefs and methods across national boundaries. The European Union, the United Nations, and many international courts and regulatory agencies now have a big say in matters that were once thought to be exclusively domestic. Globally, democratic institutions and ideals have proliferated, but they are frequently contested and implemented unevenly. An increasing number of people identify with causes and communities that cut across national borders, from human rights advocacy to environmental activism. Global governance's rise has resulted in an intricate network of agreements, treaties. America pushed hard for freer trade, co-founding the World Trade Organization and signing free-trade agreements with 20 countries as disparate as Canada, Mexico, Australia, and South Korea. Under American leadership, international trade rocketed from 39% of world GDP in 1990 to 58% in 2018 (Insights; 2025). Growing resentment towards one's financial condition as a new era of perfectionism has popped up, making insecurities for individuals, especially young adults, giving rise to consumerism. Economic globalization may also operate through global value chains, which involve the international fragmentation of production processes, where components are produced in different nations and assembled globally (Golgeci, 2021). Globalization of social life. The process by which people's lifestyles, cultures, and social structures become interconnected and influenced by global factors is referred to as social globalization. It encompasses the exchange of ideas, values, and information across borders, resulting in a more integrated world where societies share experiences and cultural practices. FOMO (fear of missing out) and the addictive nature of social media are due to unrealistic standards set by so-called influencers, making money out of people's insecurities. Image-driven platforms fuel perfectionistic standards that impact individuals at risk for eating disorders. The impact of beauty filter usage on body image, identifying body dysmorphia and social self-comparison as important mediators in the relationships between filter usage and body image-related outcomes, including a desire for weight loss, self-objectification, and anti-fat attitudes, among others (Schroeder & Morawitz, 2024). Cultural globalization. Embracing interconnectedness and valuing diversity are

the keys to finding the right balance. Because it involves the global transmission of ideas, practices, and values. The unprecedented transformation in communication led to the hybridization while also raising concerns about cultural homogenization and consumerism. Global media networks distribute cultural content to audiences all over the world, exposing them to a variety of viewpoints and artistic expressions. Social media and other online spaces enable direct cultural exchange between individuals, creating an imagery of perfectionism, but it's quite disappointing. The race-based hate crimes include crimes based on anti-white sentiment as well as against people of color, and about 61% of hate crimes based on sexual orientation target gay males (Baldwin, 2017). The climate continues to deteriorate, developed fumes are igniting the lungs of the underprivileged. Pakistan presents an interesting paradox in this context. Posing a threat to the environment as the globalized economy continues to thrive. Contaminants like greenhouse gases, plastic waste, and airborne pollutants respect no national boundaries and affect the global commons. Global supply chains have intensified resource extraction in biologically diverse regions, often with severe ecological consequences. According to a report by the International Transport Forum, CO₂ emissions from transport will increase by 16 percent by 2050. These emissions contribute to pollution, climate change, and ocean acidification around the world and have been shown to significantly impact biodiversity (Stobierski, 2021). A growing number of treaties, agreements, and organizations address global environmental issues. Developments in technology. It took 1000 years for the paper invented in China to reach Europe, but today, in integrated communities, advances are made in technology, and these aren't just limited to any region, as efforts are made to spread them across the globe. For this purpose, several advances have been made in transportation, communication, and information technology, altering the speed, scope, and intensity of global interactions. The internet and digital platforms have created virtual spaces for connection that operate largely independently of physical location. Shipping, logistics innovations, tracking systems, and other improvements have dramatically reduced the cost and increased the reliability of global trade. Cryptocurrency, algorithmic trading, and digital payment systems open up new avenues for international trade. The findings indicate that globalization has a mixed impact on youth mental health. Most respondents acknowledged positive aspects such as exposure to diverse cultures, enhanced global connectivity, and increased educational and career opportunities. Economic difficulties faced by students as they come from different backgrounds include financial burdens, including tuition fees, student loans, high cost of living in hostels, and pressure from part-time jobs just to afford their educational needs. In this time of despair, financial assistance from NGOs can be beneficial. Through social media access to a wide ocean of information that we accumulate every day. Body transformative trends, the rise of cosmetic surgery making people insecure about their natural features. Social media environments can amplify emotional swings, especially when posts are misinterpreted or when validation is inconsistent (Liao, 2025). Doing questionable deeds just for mere pennies, influencers are promoting whatever they can contribute, including exaggerating and altering information. These factors contribute to optimism and broader worldviews among students. Conversely, many participants reported experiencing stress and anxiety due to pressure to meet global standards, intense competition, and constant exposure to global news. Depressed and emotionally unstable adults has been the most frequent contention of today. Feelings of being overwhelmed and concerns regarding cultural identity were also evident. The derived

conclusion that globalization offers significant benefits simultaneously introduces psychological challenges that can negatively affect mental well-being. A majority of respondents expressed satisfaction with their coping abilities and emphasized the importance of governmental and institutional intervention. Seeking help to overcome their emotional detachment issues and reassurance regarding the future. Overall, the results support the alternative hypotheses, indicating that globalization significantly influences youth mental health. In my opinion, a few measures should be implemented in educational institutions to enhance students' capabilities, as it will eventually contribute to the betterment of our nation. Educational institutions should strengthen counseling and mental health support services. Awareness programs should be integrated into higher education curricula. Policymakers should develop youth-focused mental health policies addressing globalization-related stressors. Digital media literacy programs should be introduced to manage information overload. Cultural activities should be promoted to support identity and well-being among youth.

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